

Encouraging Reuse

Reactivating built heritage in rural historic centers

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Summary of the Action-Research¹

Encouraging Reuse was an action research Challenge conducted in the Lys Valley within the municipalities of Fontainemore and Perloz in Valle d'Aosta between spring 2024 and early 2025. The main objective was to explore how granular knowledge of built heritage (building by building) can support reuse strategies in mountain areas subject to depopulation, and what kind of supporting infrastructure is really needed to transform this knowledge into action.

The project is part of a line of work initiated by Liminal in the municipality of Pettorano sul Gizio (Abruzzo) and in Monti Prenestini (Lazio), consolidated through a master's thesis at MIT on the village of Guadagnolo (Lazio). In these contexts, a mapping method was developed and refined based on indicators visible from outside the buildings and on georeferenced digital forms that register data to detect their typology, degree of occupancy, and state of conservation. Encouraging Reuse represents the first test of this method on a larger territorial scale and with the systematic involvement of local actors and institutions in the Region of Valle d'Aosta.

The Challenge was divided into two phases. Phase 1 focused on territorial research and mapping. A mixed Liminal–MIT–local youth team mapped over 700 buildings in the hamlets of Fontainemore and Perloz, collecting standardized data and photographs for each one. At the same time, discussions, interviews, and working sessions were held with businesses, associations, services, and local governments, producing SWOT analyses and *user journeys* on the reuse of existing real estate assets. On this basis, a number of building clusters were identified as laboratories for reuse scenarios, and techniques for analyzing the data collected were tested to provide insight for these scenarios.

During Phase 1, discussions with local actors highlighted that the main bottleneck to reuse lies not so much in the absence of actually available properties or regulatory instruments, but in the lack of a third party capable of accompanying citizens along complex reuse journeys (from the idea to the economic model, from relations with the bureaucratic system to communication). This realization led to Phase 2, dedicated to defining, testing, and documenting an initial version of the role of local reuse facilitator.

In Phase 2, a group of local initiatives in various stages of development voluntarily participated in a support program marked by periodic meetings, shared diagnosis sessions, working tools (strategic canvas, financial plans, communication materials), and interim reviews. This support program,

¹ Lewin, Kurt. "Action Research and Minority Problems." *Journal of Social Issues* 2 (1946): 34–46.

designed as a case study, demonstrated in concrete terms the extent to which the facilitator can help to bring order to objectives, resources, and constraints, and to engage in brokering dialogue between funding bodies, institutions and local initiatives.

In terms of results, Encouraging Reuse has:

1. Consolidated an operational method for surveying real estate assets in small towns, using digital tools and reusable protocols.
2. Produced a georeferenced dataset and an initial training set of images useful for future methodological developments based on image-recognition.
3. Helped train young people in the area in the use of these tools and in the critical interpretation of built heritage.
4. Defined and tested, with dedicated tools and guidelines, the role of the Local Reuse Facilitator, rooted in real problems, people, and artifacts in the Lys Valley.
5. Opened a structured dialogue with GAL Valle d'Aosta and the regional government, laying the foundations for future applications of the results on a GAL or SNAI scale, and via inter-territorial cooperation projects (LEADER and Interreg programs).

Overall, the Challenge has made it possible to consolidate a two-pronged approach: on the one hand, a knowledge infrastructure on built heritage stock, and on the other, a model for supporting local initiatives that choose to invest in reuse. Some aspects initially envisaged, such as the legal analysis of tools for the reuse of real estate assets, were deliberately kept in the background in order to focus energies on developing the mapping method and experimenting with facilitation. This was due to the fact that the experience on the field proved that they were the most relevant elements for the context in question.

2.1

Challenge Results

The results of Encouraging Reuse are divided into three interconnected dimensions: the production of a new knowledge base on real estate assets and stakeholders in the Lys Valley the evolution and validation of the building-by-building mapping method; and the experimentation of a territorial function, the role of reuse facilitator, which has proven capable of supporting and unblocking reuse processes already in place. The project has also generated significant institutional effects, opening up a cycle of work and new perspectives that are now active on a regional and inter-territorial scale.

2.1.1 A New Knowledge Base for the Territory

The Challenge produced the first systematic snapshot of the building stock of many hamlets in Fontainemore and Perloz: an extensive campaign covering 18 hamlets, with 712 buildings mapped using standardized indicators and georeferenced photographs. The resulting dataset is now a unique reference point, useful for territorial planning and accessible to local authorities, LAGs, and the Region.

Alongside the physical survey, the Challenge developed an equally in-depth analysis of the actors who live in and animate the territory. Fourteen stakeholders (entrepreneurs, associations, new residents, cultural operators, and local administrators) were involved in direct interviews that led to the drafting of individual SWOT analyses² and corresponding user journeys³ of reuse, tracing the real paths of those who, with limited resources and often in solitude, try to put a property back into use. The synthesis of this material gave shape to the territorial SWOT analysis and the typical reuse journey, tools that allow for an organic reading of the difficulties, opportunities, and breaking points in the process of reactivating heritage.

The Challenge also involved 21 participants in training and dissemination activities, including 11 residents, and trained five young people from the participating municipalities in the use of digital mapping tools, thus strengthening the territory's ability to interpret and consciously manage its heritage.

² SWOT is a strategic analysis tool that organizes complex information into four categories: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. It is used to evaluate a project, organization, or context, identifying levers for action and critical issues to be addressed.

³ The user journey is a design tool that represents the path taken by a user to achieve a goal (e.g., a service or destination), highlighting needs, critical points, and opportunities for improving the experience.

Fig. 1

Example of an analytical map showing algorithmic visualizations of the state of conservation of buildings in some hamlets of Fontainemore.

2.1.2 A Scalable, Participatory, and Sound Mapping Method

Encouraging Reuse did not just apply the building-by-building mapping method previously developed: it improved it substantially, both operationally and scientifically.

Operationally, the Challenge demonstrated that the method:

1. Is scalable to multiple hamlets, multiple surveyors, and limited time frames, and lends itself to a subsequent efficiency upgrade based on automatic image recognition with human validation of sample sets.
2. Can be transferred to individuals without technical experience, as demonstrated by the direct contribution of the five young people trained to collect data in the field.
3. Produces sufficiently reliable fine-grained data to be cross-referenced with the economic, spatial, and organizational needs of local actors.

On an analytical level, the integration of user journey insights and the mapping conducted generated three experimental analyses dedicated to building typology, occupancy levels, and state of conservation. Thanks to these analyses, it was possible to verify which building clusters were compatible with specific reuse strategies and which, on the other hand, required disproportionate investment or operational complexity for intended programs.

The Challenge also produced a training set of images derived from data collected manually using uniform criteria: the first step towards future automation of the mapping activities. Overall, the method emerges from the Challenge validated, enriched, and systematized in a dedicated guideline that documents its applicability, limitations, and potential for evolution.

2.1.3 Four Territorial Reuse Strategies

Listening to stakeholders and summarizing their territorial insights led to the definition of four reuse strategies, recognized by the project partners as relevant to the dynamics at play in the Lys Valley. These strategies focused on:

1. Strengthening productive initiatives and services in the most vital hamlets.
2. Activate shared spaces and local services in underutilized areas.
3. Supporting projects that bring new permanent residents to small municipalities.
4. Enhancing cultural and social activities that bring marginal heritage back into circulation.

These strategies were then empirically verified through the survey, which made it possible to identify building clusters that were suitable or unsuitable for the different trajectories. The comparison between expectations and data-based analysis allowed for useful effort/output conclusions to be drawn. Some buildings were strategic in terms of location or type but required costly interventions. Others, although located differently from the initial strategic assumptions, appeared more realistic and sustainable for the projects that local actors aspire to. This cross-analysis led to the definition of a shared territorial scenario, which was presented publicly to local administrators, the local LAG, and the regional government.

2.1.4 Defining the Role of the Local Reuse Facilitator

The most significant result of Phase 1 was the definition of the role of Local Reuse Facilitator, which was not envisaged in this form in the initial project proposal. While it was initially assumed that the main obstacle to reuse was linked to the fragmentation of ownership, for which the solution could be of a legal nature, fieldwork showed that the real bottleneck is organizational and human: the operational isolation of entrepreneurs, associations, and new residents who drive activities that are essential to the life of the valley.

Fig. 2

Diagram of the relationship between the local reuse facilitator, local authorities, and beneficiaries of the facilitation process.

The facilitator, as defined in the dedicated guidelines, is a continuous support figure that helps to:

1. Clarify objectives and priorities.
2. Build sustainable economic models.
3. Interpret spatial needs and match them with available assets.
4. Connect to the right resources or professionals at the right time.
5. Broker institutional relations and communication.
6. Maintain continuity throughout the process, also offering a space for confidential discussion at critical moments.

This figure does not "bring solutions from outside," but rather fits into individual trajectories already in progress, helping to strengthen them.

Fig. 3
Diagram of the phases imagined in a facilitation process during the design phase, which can also be activated in different combinations and sequences according to the needs of beneficiaries with active initiatives.

2.1.5 Experimentation With the Facilitator

In Phase 2, the role of the facilitator was tested by contacting 15 actors involved in Phase 1, 6 of which expressed their interest, 5 underwent facilitation processes, and 2 completed the journey as planned during the initial dialogue phase. The experiment showed that the facilitator can:

1. Give structure and clarity to initially fragmented ideas.
2. Help build or improve business models, economic and financial plans, and user profiles, even for activities beyond the launch phase.
3. Accelerate the identification of suitable properties using the mapping dataset.
4. Facilitate interaction with municipalities, LAGs, property owners, and professionals.
5. Support beneficiaries in times of uncertainty or impasse, providing a space for listening and guidance.

Fig. 4
Table of facilitation phases actually activated by beneficiaries during Phase 2, indicating the frequency of use of each service.

The journeys initiated produced concrete progress for beneficiaries involved, such as: clarification of strategic positioning, definition of economic models, identification of compatible properties, preparation of professional communication materials and structured institutional dialogues. The experience made it possible to further refine the facilitation method and consolidate the operational guidelines, which can now be used in other territorial contexts.

2.1.6 Institutional Results and Forthcoming Opportunities

At the institutional level, the Challenge generated three main results. First, it inaugurated a new and structured dialogue between municipalities, LAG, and the regional government on the condition of built heritage and the difficulties faced by those seeking to enhance it. The door remains open today to subsequent phases of work, which will be able to capitalize on the results already achieved.

Second, it made it clear that in order to function effectively and sustainably, the facilitator must be placed at an appropriate level, such as a LAG, SNAI area, Comunità Montana, or regional department, where it is possible to build trust over time and accompany a minority of actors active in a profound and continuous manner.

Third, it laid the foundations for two institutional paths that are now active:

1. The executive planning of the LEADER inter-territorial cooperation⁴ Liminal Embassy, which involves four Italian LAGs and which, thanks to the Encouraging Reuse experience, will aim to consolidate the implementation of some of the elements developed in various regions of the country.
2. Participation in the application for a European Horizon RIA project, coordinated by the Politecnico di Milano and developed with an international consortium involving the University of Greenwich, Universidad de Alcalá, Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Istanbul Technical University, University of Vlorë, University of Dowa, Smart Silvan, Botanical City, Habitat Unit – TU Berlin, together with municipal administrations, experts, and businesses. In this context, facilitation models and digital support tools for facilitators could be tested in several territories, verifying the transnational transversality of what has been developed thanks to local specificities in the context of Valle d'Aosta.

Overall, Encouraging Reuse has generated a knowledge base, a consolidated method, and an operational model ready to be applied on a larger scale, contributing to the territorial planning and local development of Valle d'Aosta and other similar contexts, and laying the foundations for more operational and high-impact phases in the coming years.

⁴ LEADER is the EU program for rural development based on a community-led approach. LEADER strategies are implemented by LAGs and operate in homogeneous territorial areas, where communities, administrations, and businesses co-design local development interventions.

2.2

Contextual Overview

2.2.1 Objectives and Territorial Context

The Encouraging Reuse Challenge took place in the Lys Valley, a side valley of Valle d'Aosta where small mid-mountain municipalities such as Fontainemore and Perloz are simultaneously managing three structural dynamics: the dispersion of settlements across numerous hamlets, the aging and reduction of the resident population, and the growing difficulty in maintaining services, economic activities, and built heritage. In this context, the building stock—which includes homes, former production facilities, mixed-use buildings, and properties that are oversized for current families—is both a potential resource and a concrete constraint. Many buildings are empty or underutilized, often in complex physical conditions, with fragmented ownership and high renovation costs compared to the investment capacity of those who would like to use them.

This picture is not only local: it reflects a broader transformation of Italy's inland areas, where public policy instruments struggle to reconcile the strategic horizon (regional programs, LAGs⁵, SNAls⁶, European tenders) with the daily reality of those who try, often alone, to reactivate a property or business in a village. This is precisely where the question that gave rise to Encouraging Reuse comes in: what is needed, in concrete terms, to make the reuse of existing heritage a viable option for mountain areas? And what kind of infrastructure (informational, organizational or relational) can help bridge the gap between policies and grassroots initiatives?

2.2.2 Genealogy of the Method Applied

This general question comes out of the genealogy of the applied research experiences that Liminal brings to the Lys Valley. The work on building-by-building surveys began in Pettorano sul Gizio, in Abruzzo, during the Rebuilding the Edge Challenge, where an initial survey of the historic center was carried out. This was a systematic survey based on a digital form that records, building by building, indicators visible from the public right of way on the state of conservation and actual use. The results showed that, in contexts marked by depopulation, reading the heritage from what is actually visible can provide a much more realistic picture than that which is offered by statistics or perceptions alone.

⁵ Local Action Groups (LAGs) are public-private partnerships that manage the European LEADER program in rural areas defined as LAG areas. A LAG area is a socio-economically coherent territory, often a group of rural municipalities, which develops a large-scale local development strategy, selects projects to be funded, and coordinates the public and private actors involved.

⁶ The National Strategy for Internal Areas (SNAl) is the Italian policy that supports mountainous and peripheral territories characterized by low accessibility to essential services. Each SNAl area is a homogeneous territory composed of several municipalities that share similar problems and potential: the strategy intervenes on a large territorial scale, integrating education, healthcare, mobility, and local development through projects coordinated between several administrations.

The next phase takes place in Monti Prenestini (Lazio) through the Challenge Liminal Lab Monti Prenestini. Here, the same approach was entrusted to a group of 18 participants, who were asked to map four villages in a single day. The experiment served to understand whether the method was transferable and whether data collection could be carried out in a coordinated manner even by non-specialists, provided they were equipped with clear tools and technical support. The experiment confirmed that mapping can become a participatory activity and not remain the prerogative of technicians alone.

At this point, the method was scrutinized by academic research: Annabel Consilvio's master's thesis at the Department of Urban Studies and Planning at MIT, dedicated to the village of Guadagnolo⁷ explored the methodological and statistical aspects of the work, formalizing indicators, scores, and analysis procedures, and testing the link between data collected in the field, regeneration strategies, and actual financing vehicles. It is at this stage that the potential of the method as a tool that is not only descriptive but also predictive and supportive of decision-making became clear, particularly when applied to sufficiently large samples of buildings.

Encouraging Reuse represented the next step along this trajectory: applying the method on a larger territorial scale, testing its participatory dimension and, above all, verifying how it can interact with the institutional machinery that governs these territories. The decision to work with GAL Valle d'Aosta and the municipalities of Fontainemore and Perloz stemmed precisely from the need to place the experiment in a context where settlement fragmentation is evident and where there is already an entity—the LAG—that operates on the border between regional policies and local initiatives.

2.2.3 The Challenge Partnership

The Encouraging Reuse project was promoted by Liminal in partnership with:

1. **GAL Valle d'Aosta**
A key player in terms of local positioning, coordination with municipalities, and framing the work within LEADER strategies as well as, more generally, rural development in Valle d'Aosta.
2. **Municipalities of Fontainemore and Perloz**
Local authorities that made their territory available, accompanied the work on the ground, and hosted the feedback sessions.
3. **MIT-Italy Program**
A university body that made it possible to involve international researchers and students with advanced skills in geospatial planning and mapping, linking the Valle d'Aosta experiment to an ongoing research project.
4. **Fondazione Compagnia di San Paolo**
The main funding body that made it possible to bring these dimensions together through financial support and the invitation to think of the Challenge's objective as a set of guidelines on civic participation in territorial regeneration processes.

⁷ A. Consilvio, *Encouraging Reuse in Rural Italy: A Case Study of Small Depopulating Towns*, Cambridge (MA), Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2024, available on MIT DSpace: <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/156114>.

Encouraging Reuse was not just a technical exercise in mapping, but an opportunity to verify, in a real context, whether a certain way of reading the territory and accompanying its actors could become a stable part of rural development policies. The main objectives of the initiative reflect this ambition: to provide the Lys Valley with an accurate and shared reading of its building stock; to test the possibility of constructing a participatory mapping that also generates value for those who participate in it; to identify, based on the data, a number of clusters of buildings and exemplary situations on which to reflect in depth; and to use these real cases to design and test tools and guidelines that can facilitate the processes of reusing real estate assets in contexts such as the one described. Only against this broader backdrop—made up of concrete problems, methodological genealogies, and institutional alliances—can the logic of the methodological approach be fully understood.

2.3

Methodological Approach

The methodological approach of Encouraging Reuse was constructed progressively, following an experimental logic. Each step was designed to open up space for the next, leaving room to correct the course based on what emerged from the fieldwork. The project was divided into two closely related phases:

1. **Phase 1**
Dedicated to building a granular knowledge of the territory and bringing out real strategies and obstacles to heritage reuse from local actors.
2. **Phase 2**
In which the solution—embodied in the role of the local reuse facilitator—was tested as a pilot service to accompany local initiatives.

The basic idea was to move from listening to those who are already trying to bring the territory to life, to direct observation of the buildings and their uses, to the identification and testing of an operational tool capable of unlocking and facilitating the process of adoption and reuse of underutilized spaces.

2.3.1 Phase 1: From the Building Survey to the Role of the Facilitator

2.3.1.1 Initial Dialogue and Preparation for Field Activities

Phase 1 began with discussions with GAL Valle d'Aosta, the municipalities of Fontainemore and Perloz, and an initial group of key players in the Lys Valley. Through preparatory meetings, the scope of the work area, the partners' expectations, and the main issues surrounding the relationship between real estate, depopulation, and local development were clarified. On this basis, a set of 18 hamlets was defined on which to focus the fieldwork.

At the same time, the team adapted the mapping method already tested in Abruzzo and Monti Prenestini to the context of the Lys Valley, defining a set of building-by-building indicators divided into three main categories: type, degree of occupancy, and state of conservation. The indicators were translated into a georeferencing digital form, designed to be used in a standardized manner by multiple surveyors.

2.3.1.2 Dialogue with Local Stakeholders and Individual SWOTs

With the entire project team in the area, an extensive series of meetings and interviews was conducted before and during the mapping process with individuals who, in various capacities, deal with the built heritage: owners, entrepreneurs, managers of commercial and accommodation businesses, associations, new residents, cultural operators, and institutional representatives. Each conversation was systematized in an individual SWOT analysis, which reflected, from the point of view of each stakeholder, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to the area and the use of the local built heritage.

These initial conversations provided the basic material for understanding not only the physical condition of the buildings, but also the paths, ambitions, and frustrations of those who are already trying, often in difficult conditions, to bring parts of the heritage back into use.

2.3.1.3 Building-by-Building Survey

At the same time, a building-by-building mapping campaign was carried out in selected hamlets of the two municipalities. The survey was conducted on foot, hamlet by hamlet, filling in a digital form for each building and taking photographs of the facades. Five young people from the area, trained in the method before starting, assisted in this activity, thus integrating local knowledge into the survey process.

The result was a georeferenced dataset of 712 buildings between Fontainemore and Perloz, which provides a detailed picture of the built heritage in the study area and allowed the team to refine certain aspects of the mapping method during the course of the work, testing its validity on a larger scale and with participatory involvement.

Fig. 5

Maps of the main town of the municipality of Perloz drawn up on the basis of an analysis of the data collected. From left: overall size of buildings, state of conservation, level of occupancy.

2.3.1.4 Interviews and Individual User Journeys

After an initial introductory meeting, many stakeholders were contacted again during the mapping period. This made it possible to go beyond the static snapshot provided by the individual SWOT analysis and to reconstruct, on a

case-by-case basis, the specific path that each person had taken, or was taking, to purchase, renovate, reuse, or generate income from a property.

These *follow-ups* gave rise to individual user journeys, which describe step by step the typical path to reuse: the decision to invest, exploring the area and searching for a property, the relationship with the owner, the administrative steps, the construction of the economic model, access to incentives or financing, and the opening and management of the business. A comparison of the different paths highlighted recurring issues: difficulty in navigating regulations and offices, difficulty in building solid economic plans, isolation in dialogue with institutions, high renovation costs, and lack of time and skills to structure communication about the business.

2.3.1.5 From a Mosaic of Case Studies to a Territorial Diagnosis

The individual SWOTs were then aggregated into an overall territorial SWOT that incorporated the reflections that emerged from the mapping to describe the economic, social, tourist, infrastructural, and real estate dimensions of the territory. In parallel, the synthesis of the user journeys led to the construction of a typical path of reuse in the Lys Valley: a unique trajectory that condenses the recurring obstacles and steps that emerged from the different cases.

This dual summary, territorial SWOT and typical user journey, made it clear that the problem is not so much a lack of ideas or initiatives, but rather the fragility of the ecosystem that should support them over time.

Fig. 6

Summary of the typical user journey developed from local experiences of real estate reuse, whether completed, ongoing, or in their initial stages.

2.3.1.6 Development of Reuse Strategies

Based on this qualitative framework, four reuse strategies were developed at the territorial level, designed as macro-programming guidelines built around the people, activities, and ambitions already present in the territory. In simplified form, these strategies concerned:

1. The strengthening of productive and service initiatives already active in the most vital districts.
2. The activation of shared spaces and local services in underutilized areas of the territory.
3. Enhancing projects that bring new permanent residents to the municipalities.
4. Supporting cultural and social initiatives capable of bringing marginal built heritage back into circulation.

Only then were these strategies compared with the results of the building-by-building survey. The aim was not to use the data to make decisions based on a strictly technical approach, but to verify the extent to which the insights and priorities expressed by the actors were reflected in the built heritage actually available: which building clusters were consistent with the spatial requirements of the strategies; where the heritage displayed realistic conditions for reuse; where, on the contrary, investments would be too high or conditions difficult to modify.

Fig. 7

Reuse scenarios in a hamlet, developed in relation to one of the strategies identified and the main spatial, economic, and organizational constraints.

In this sense, mapping made the relationship between effort and result visible: it helped to balance the ambitions and resources of individual strategies with the characteristics of the buildings actually available, distinguishing, for example, between properties that were totally abandoned but perfectly located for a certain function, and properties in good condition, with low reuse costs, but located in different positions from those initially imagined. Mapping therefore served as an empirical basis for control: not so much a prescriptive tool as a way of testing the soundness and feasibility of the strategies that emerged from the listening process.

2.3.1.7 Identification of Instruments to Encourage Reuse

When the project was conceived, the initial assumption was that the main problem with reuse lay primarily in the forms of ownership and the legal tools available to institutions to intervene on fragmented, inherited, and underutilized properties. It was expected that the main focus would be on innovative formulas to unlock 'blocked' properties and aggregate them into new vehicles: from community cooperatives to simple company structures in which different owners contribute properties to a 'fund' geared towards a shared business project, to hybrid public-private instruments designed for geographically decentered hospitality or collective uses.

Fieldwork revealed a different picture: it is not so much the absence of regulatory instruments or aggregation formulas that blocks processes, but rather the operational isolation of those who try, often with limited means, to bring the territory to life. It is the local 'champions', both in the for-profit and non-profit sectors, the people who invest time and resources in activities that are difficult to make work but fundamental to the life of the valley, who find themselves most exposed. They struggle to navigate bureaucracy, accounting, relations with institutions, the search for suitable properties, crisis management, and changes in the core phase of their enterprises. It is not so much a question of lacking 'goodwill' as of the ability to cope with a combination of diverse problems at the pace that their often small-scale projects would require.

This awareness gradually led to the emergence of the figure of the 'territorial reuse facilitator': not a new office or someone who 'brings ideas from

outside', but a continuous support function aimed at those already on the territory. A figure capable of helping:

1. Clarify objectives and priorities.
2. Build sustainable economic models.
3. Interpret spatial needs and match them with available assets.
4. Build bridges, at the right time, with resources, professionals, and key administrative interlocutors.
5. Structure communication and relations with institutions and partners.
6. Maintain continuity over time, meeting after meeting, also offering a confidential listening space for those who tend to find themselves alone on their journey.

The principle that emerged was simple: built heritage survives when the local area thrives. Today, the most promising lever is not so much the abstract aggregation of real estate or the arrival of external investment, but rather targeted support for those few players who can trigger virtuous dynamics that benefit everyone else.

Fig. 8

Operational guidelines for the role of the local reuse facilitator.

Phase 1 concluded with a public presentation at a meeting in the municipality of Perloz with representatives from the Valle d'Aosta Region, GAL Valle d'Aosta, municipal administrators, and local actors. On this occasion, the results of the mapping, the territorial SWOT analysis, the typical reuse process, the strategies identified, and the proposed institutional and operational architecture for the facilitator were shared. The presentation was followed by small group discussions, which took the form of a focus group

aimed at exploring the value, limitations, and operability of the proposals that emerged, thus creating the conditions for moving from conceptual definition to operational experimentation.

2.3.2 Phase 2: Experimenting With Facilitation as a Territorial Service

Phase 2 aimed to test, in real conditions, the role of the local reuse facilitator, verifying what actual services they could offer, how they could do so, and what results were perceived by local actors. The reference model was that of business facilitation inspired by Ernesto Sirolli: voluntary, non-directive support, in which it is the beneficiary who asks for support and guides the pace of the process. The facilitator does not 'seek out clients' but makes himself available to those who express a concrete interest and demonstrates a desire to take advantage of this resource for their own benefit.

2.3.2.1 Activation and Selection of Participants

The LAG contacted about fifteen people and initiatives already encountered in Phase 1, inviting them to participate in the experiment. Bilateral face-to-face meetings were organized with those who expressed interest, during which the functioning of the process, mutual expectations, and the limits of the support available were explained. Each meeting ended with a self-assessment exercise to identify together the priorities to work on. Only those who, after this first phase, chose to contact Liminal again actually started the program, in line with the principle that it is up to the beneficiary to decide whether or not to commit to long-term support.

2.3.2.2 Personalized Support Journeys

With the small group of initiatives that confirmed their availability, a mainly online facilitation process was launched, lasting between 3 and 6 months, punctuated by periodic meetings. Each meeting focused on one or more specific elements of the project: clarification of the idea and positioning, development of business models and economic-financial plans, definition of user profiles, spatial requirements and property requirements, targeted use of mapping data where relevant, communication strategies and brand kits, and building relationships with municipalities, owners, or other key players.

Each session ended with one or two 'next steps' assigned to both the beneficiary and the facilitator, in order to maintain a sustainable pace consistent with the principle that it is the beneficiary who decides whether and how to proceed. In several cases, the facilitator also played a supporting role at critical moments, offering a confidential space for discussion of doubts, fears, frustrations, and difficult choices that accompany any entrepreneurial or associative path in fragile contexts.

Fig. 9

Examples of outputs developed by one of the participants who activated the largest number of stages in the facilitation process: from context analysis to bottleneck identification, from strategic definition to economic structuring, from property search to the development of new relationships, and from the drafting of economic plans to brand repositioning.

2.3.2.3 Observation of Results and Reflections

During Phase 2, not only was the progress of individual projects monitored, but also the overall functioning of the service: what types of support were requested, which skills were most critical, which conditions favored continuity, and where, on the other hand, interruptions occurred. Some paths were limited to a single targeted intervention; others led to the definition of more structured growth strategies, comprehensive economic plans, professional communication tools, and the practical use of data collected in Phase 1 to identify properties suitable for specific projects.

Phase 2 concluded with a local public presentation in the municipality of Fontainemore and a presentation at the Valle d'Aosta Regional Authority, attended by LAG Valle d'Aosta and regional representatives from several departments. The results of the experiment were shared at these events: the value perceived by the beneficiaries, the limitations linked to the difficulty of identifying and supporting individuals with the appropriate skills, and the need to place the facilitator on a supra-municipal level (LAG, SNAI area, Comunità Montana), where even a few successful cases can generate significant change.

2.4

Challenges and Limitations

The experimental nature of the Challenge led to several structural limitations of the process. These were not failures, but rather elements that clarified how the methods and tools developed through Encouraging Reuse can fully express their potential going forward.

A first limitation concerned the technological component. Although the integration of automatic image recognition techniques was not among the initial objectives, it was nevertheless a prospect that the project hoped to pursue at a later stage, going beyond the preliminary verification of its feasibility. However, the reality of the fieldwork required the team to focus the energies on manual surveying, building a reliable dataset, and developing rigorous analytical algorithms. Mapping did, however, allow the team to generate an initial training set useful for future developments and for preliminary testing of artificial intelligence for the recognition of indicators through images. However the operational use of AI remains a task that will require more time to flush out.

Fig. 10

Map of the municipalities of Perloz, Lillianes, and Fontainemore with an indication of the hamlets mapped as part of the Challenge.

Even the building-by-building mapping, despite producing valuable results, encountered intrinsic limitations. The fragmentation of the heritage and the abundance of units in the two areas made a total survey impossible—yet another goal that was not initially conceived but desirable to the research team—directing the work towards the hamlets that were a priority for the administrations. Furthermore, the limited involvement of the municipal technical offices, which were busy with very heavy ordinary workloads, did not allow for a full exploration of how data collection could be integrated into local administrative processes, as was the case in similar contexts during other initiatives.

The experimentation with the role of facilitator highlighted an issue of scale. The number of initiatives in the municipalities involved in the project is too small to continuously evaluate the typical mechanisms of facilitation, including the natural decrease in participants over time. The process confirmed the value of the facilitator, but also made it clear that this tool requires a larger pool of actors and a longer-term presence to function in a stable manner: scales such as LAGs, SNAs, or small regions, where trust can be consolidated and where even a few success stories generate significant effects.

Finally, the relationship between mapping and strategies highlighted a structural limitation in the initial theoretical model. The expectation that mapping and local strategies would converge in a single operational tool proved to be partially unrealistic: mapping proved to be very useful as a verification tool, but not always as a direct driver of action at the municipal level. Its usefulness appears to be much greater at larger scales—LAGs, SNAI, Region—where fine-grained knowledge can inform planning and investment, while local action depends largely on specific people and conditions.

In summary, these limitations paint a clear picture: the method works, but requires broader contexts than those established on the basis of the initial project assumptions; facilitation produces value, but needs a larger pool of potential beneficiaries; AI optimizations are technically possible, but requires more time; mapping is valuable, but its function varies depending on the scale.

2.5

Conclusions

Encouraging Reuse has shown that addressing the issue of reuse in small municipalities requires a combination of fine-grained knowledge, listening to the territory, and operational tools capable of sustaining the efforts of those who already animate the place continuously. The Challenge has generated a new informational base for the two municipalities of the Lys Valley involved, a significant methodological evolution, and a facilitation model that has proven to have a concrete impact on the trajectories of real initiatives.

One of the most important contributions of the project was to clarify the two-sided structure of the method: on the one hand, mapping, which produces valuable local data and is most useful on a larger scale (LAG, SNAI, Region); on the other hand, facilitation, which operates at the local level by supporting local 'champions', the people whose initiatives make any regeneration process possible. The two components do not coincide, but reinforce each other: mapping creates knowledge and perspectives for policies, while facilitation gives continuity and concreteness to the initiatives that bring heritage to life.

Encouraging Reuse has also confirmed that the data collected through mapping is not only useful for individual paths accompanied by the facilitator. It can be integrated into a broader ecosystem of tools, showing synergies already in place with other Liminal lines of work. In particular, integration with the methods developed through the Digital Paths and Weaving Urban Data Challenges⁸ highlights how the same information infrastructure can generate value on three horizons:

1. Immediate, thanks to datasets and georeferenced images that feed exploratory, educational, and tourist services, updating tools such as Google Street View and improving the readability of territories.
2. Medium term, supporting facilitation, guidance, and local planning processes thanks to the possibility of identifying suitable properties, reading spatial needs, and creating visual previews of possible changes.
3. Long term, by contributing to the definition of more informed, coherent, and realistic policies, thanks to structured databases useful to LAGs, regions, and European programs.

In this sense, Encouraging Reuse is not an isolated project, but part of a broader strategy: to build an integrated knowledge infrastructure that allows citizens, facilitators, local authorities, and institutional decision-makers to work from different perspectives on a unique minor heritage. The Challenge has therefore contributed not only to understanding the Lys Valley, but also to outlining an exportable model: a scalable combination of mapping, listening, and facilitation.

The facilitator experiment demonstrated the transformative potential of this role: offering continuity, clarity, connections, and support at critical moments; accompanying economic plans, spatial choices, and institutional relationships; creating trust. At the same time, it highlighted that, in order to function fully, this role needs to be placed on a larger scale—LAG area, SNAI area, Comunità Montana, or Region—and requires operational continuity that only a stable infrastructure can guarantee.

The institutional outcomes confirm this trajectory: the open dialogue with the Valle d'Aosta Region, the executive planning of the Liminal Embassy cooperation, and participation in the European Horizon RIA project show how the work carried out has already become a lever for future initiatives, capable of bringing experimentation to broader contexts, with more mature tools and networks of national and international partners.

Ultimately, Encouraging Reuse has brought to the fore an integrated approach that is now ready to enter a more operational phase: a combination of territorial databases, facilitation services, and institutional alliances that can contribute to the development of more informed policies and, at the same time, support initiatives that bring heritage to life in mountain areas. This combination, as a whole, concretely reflects the principles of the European

⁸ G. D'Agostino, G. Pizzi, N. Delgado Alcega, *Weaving Urban Data: Laying the Foundations for Smart Villages through Participatory Mapping* (2025), Liminal APS, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17101800.

Smart Villages⁹ paradigm: the integration of digital tools and the daily needs of communities, social activation through support pathways, and the construction of multi-level governance that connects citizens, local authorities, and regional actors. This work has also given rise to two distinct lines of development, each with its own tools, timing, and methods of intervention: on the one hand, the construction of knowledge and analytical infrastructures that support decision-making processes; on the other, the direct support of local actors through facilitation and reactivation pathways. These are two complementary components of our broader toolkit for catalyzing territorial regeneration, which require differentiated but coordinated approaches. Thanks to the results obtained, this method—which combines knowledge, participation, and operational support—can now be put at the service of territories facing similar challenges, in Valle d’Aosta and elsewhere.

⁹ *Smart Villages* are an initiative of the European Union’s rural development policy that promotes digital and innovative solutions to improve sustainability and quality of life in rural areas.

3.1

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